

Supplementary Information:

Investigating the effectiveness of multimodal data in forecasting SARS-COV-2 case surges

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under three temporal configurations: t_{-1} , t_{-2} , and $t_{-1} + t_{-2}$ lags. Classification accuracy evaluates model performance on discrete surge labels of (A) hospital admissions and (C) death counts. Mean absolute error (MAE) quantifies regression performance for continuous surge intensity i.e., (B) hospital admission surge values and (D) death counts. Bars denote country-specific results.. Note: MAE for XGBoost model trained on data from India is not shown here due to high MAE values >1.5 (Table S5)

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Figure S38: Country-wise performance of bi-feature models for predicting surge labels for surge in death counts. Prediction accuracy for five-class surge classification using pairwise combinations of feature modalities evaluated at prediction lags ranging from t_{-1} to t_{-4} weeks. Each panel represents a country, and each line corresponds to a different feature-pair model.

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Figure S40: Country-wise performance of single-feature models for predicting surge ratios for surge in case counts. Prediction accuracy for five-class surge classification using individual feature modalities (mobility, tweets, reported cases, policy stringency, and mutation prevalence) evaluated at different prediction lags (t_{-1} to t_{-4} weeks). Each panel corresponds to a country, and lines represent the performance of models trained using a single feature category. The y-axis scale is adjusted per panel to highlight differences across lag windows.

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